

Graphite nanopowder chemically modified electrode for hydrogen peroxide sensing

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Abstract : Chemically modified electrodes (CMEs) are the recent impeccable achievements of electrochemists. The point lies in making simpler CMEs without any complicated methods of preparations. Here in, we present a graphite nanopowder (GNP) coated glassy carbon electrode (GCE), designated as GCE/GNP, for simple electrochemical sensing of H_2O_2 in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution. Note that H_2O_2 is extensively used in cosmetics and food products (as preservative in milk) and if the usable concentration exceeds certain limit then it may lead to severe health hazards. Thus, simple and low cost detection methodologies are most needed for the real sample analysis. Meanwhile, carbon nanomaterial have attracted great interest among researchers due to their unique structures, good electrical, mechanical, and chemical properties. GNP is one of such carbon nanomaterial which is very cheap and easy available in market. Here in we report a GCE/GNP modified electrode, without any enzyme and addition redox mediator, as a sensor for H_2O_2 . CV of the GCE/GNP showed a H_2O_2 -reduction peak at -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution. Control experiments with activated charcoal modified and unmodified glassy carbon electrodes failed to show any such marked H_2O_2 reduction signal. Furthermore, GCE/GNP was subjected to amperometric $i-t$ curve technique which gave significant response to H_2O_2 -sensing. Biochemicals like cysteine, ascorbic acid, uric acid, dopamine and nitrate were also tested for interference.

Keywords : Graphite nanopowder, chemically modified electrode, H_2O_2 , sensing.

Introduction

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is widely being used in milk products (as preservative), cosmetic creams (as bleaching agent), medicine (as disinfectant), other daily use products such as tooth pastes (whitening), hair conditioners, shampoos etc. The recommended concentration limit regarded as safe by the FDA (food and drug administration) is 80 ppm or 6%¹. However, if concentration limit exceeds, as H_2O_2 is a good oxidizing agent, it shows a corrosive effect on skin and other surfaces. More than 20% concentration is severely hazardous. In the conventional methods of sensing H_2O_2 , basically colorimetric and fluorescence techniques are employed. However, for colorimetric detection, derivatization of H_2O_2 has to be done before sensing as it lacks chromophores or must be coupled with fluorescence probe for fluorescence technique². Literature report shows many redox mediator based CMEs³ which has lengthy and difficult preparation methods. A couple of them also show some draw backs due to

lack of stability.

CME is an excellent way of selective electrochemical sensing of various analytes and has become interest of many researchers in recent few years⁴. In this work, we are reporting a commercially available graphite nanopowder (GNP) modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE) designated as GCE/GNP to sense H_2O_2 . It has a simple method of preparation using cheaper carbon nanomaterial and no other extra binders or surfactants or redox mediators are used. GNP is a fine powder with a pore size of 400 nm^{5,6}. Simple cyclic voltammetry technique (CV) and amperometric technique is used for performing experiment using 10 mL of nitrogen purged (N_2) phosphate buffer solution (PBS) of pH 7 as an electrolyte. The prepared electrode (GCE/GNP) showed a good response when amperometric $i-t$ curve was performed with spiking 500 μM H_2O_2 at regular intervals. It also sensed H_2O_2 in presence of cysteine (Cys), ascorbic acid (AA), uric acid (UA), dopamine (DA), nitrate (NO_3^-),

without any significant interference. Control experiments using bare GCE and activated charcoal modified GCE were also performed which showed feeble currents.

Experimental

Graphite nanopowder (purity assay = ~98%, 400 nm pore size) received from SRL India. Hydrogen peroxide (30%) obtained from Rankem (India) and stored in refrigerator. Activated charcoal obtained with that of Raman spectroscopy. N₂ purged phosphate buffer solution of pH 7 (supporting electrolyte) was prepared with 2.17 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate and 1.17 g of sodium hydrogen phosphate in 500 mL of deionized double distilled (DD) water. Biochemicals like ascorbic acid, uric acid, dopamine, cysteine, nitrate of ACS-certified grade were used.

Cyclic voltammetric and amperometric experiments were performed on CHI model 660 work station USA with 10 mL working volume. The three working electrode system used was of Ag/AgCl with 3 M KCl as reference electrode, GNP modified GCE as working electrode with the surface area of 0.0707 cm², platinum wire as counter electrode.

The GCE surface was mechanically cleaned by polishing with 1 μm alumina powder, followed by washing with acetone and DD water. Pretreatment was done by performing CV for 20 cycles in 10 mL PBS at a potential window of -0.2 to 1.2 V Ag/AgCl. 2 mg of GNP is dispersed in 500 μL of ethanol and sonicated for 15 min. 5 μL of this solution is drop coated on the cleaned GCE surface. Air dried for 5 ± 3 min.

Optimization is done by performing CV with a three electrode system of modified electrode, platinum wire; reference electrode in 10 mL N₂ purged PBS for 20 cycles in a potential window of -0.7 to 0.5 V at 50 mV s⁻¹. Followed by checking stability for more 20 cycles in the same potential window.

After stabilizing electrode, it is exposed to 500 μM H₂O₂ dissolved pH 7 PBS. CV is performed in the potential window of -0.7 to 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl at 10 mV s⁻¹ for 4 cycles. A blank (without H₂O₂) is also checked with just 10 mL of N₂ PBS in the same potential window and scan rate. Amperometric *i-t* curve is performed with a

potential of -0.19 V vs Ag/AgCl with spiking 50 μL of 500 μM H₂O₂. In the same potential window biochemicals are tested for interference.

Results and discussion

In Fig. 1(A), the comparison of CV response of GCE/GNP without (a) and with 500 μM H₂O₂ (b) in pH 7 N₂ purged PBS is shown. There is a marked increase in reduction current. Although the reduction starts at 0 V but a distinct peak of complete reduction is obtained at -0.5 V. A control experiment in which the CV response of bare GCE (unmodified GCE) with and without H₂O₂ were also compared. Feeble current response is obtained at -0.4 V which is very less compared to the optimal CME (data not enclosed). Another control experiment with activated charcoal (AC) modified GCE with and without 500 μM H₂O₂ was also performed. Current obtained is ten times smaller than the current obtained with GCE/GNP@H₂O₂. These control experiments showed that bare GCE and AC modified GCE shows negligible H₂O₂ reduction when compared to the optimal GCE/GNP (data not enclosed).

Fig. 1. (A) CV responses of GCE@GNP without (a) and with (b) 500 μM H₂O₂ at $v = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ in pH 7 PBS.

In Fig. 2(A), an amperometric *i-t* response obtained by spiking 50 μL of 500 μM H₂O₂ at regular intervals of 100 s for 600 s at an applied potential of -0.19 V with GCE/GNP@H₂O₂ in N₂ purged pH 7 PBS is shown. A consecutive reduction response of H₂O₂ is obtained. On plotting a calibration graph between current and concentration (B), linear plot is obtained which indicates that as the concentration of H₂O₂ increases, the reduction cur-

Fig. 2. (A) Amperometric response of GCE/GNP + H₂O₂ with spiking of 50 μL of 500 μM H₂O₂ at regular intervals of 100 s at potential -0.19 V. (B) Calibration plot of current vs concentration of H₂O₂. (C) Illustrates amperometric response of various biochemicals tested for interference.

rent increases. The detection limit of H₂O₂ by GCE/GNP calculated from the calibration plot is 12 μM shows the amperometric *i-t* curve response of H₂O₂ on GCE/GNP in presence of various biochemicals : (a) is the H₂O₂, followed by spiking of 1 mM each of Cys (b), AA (c), UA (d), DA (e), NO₃²⁻ (f). Negligible signal is given by the biochemicals. From the above results it is obvious that the GNP modified electrode showed better electrochemical H₂O₂ sensing response than that of the other low cost and normally available carbon materials even in presence of other biochemicals.

Conclusion

A simple GNP modified GCE was prepared that could sense H₂O₂ selectively. There are no expensive redox mediators, binders and surfactants used. This is extendable to disposable screen printed electrode. Biochemicals like Cys, AA, UA, nitrate, DA gave negligible response which shows the electrode is selectivity towards H₂O₂.

As it is selective it can be applied to test the real samples like milk, cosmetic cream etc. for detecting H₂O₂ in them.

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